

This skills sheet summarizes the most commonly used **Unix** commands in the field of **bioinformatics**. It was created by the [e-learning working group of the French Institute of Bioinformatics](#). The objective is to define **the expected Unix skills in bioinformatics**. These skills are organized according to **increasing levels of difficulty** and thematic groups. The skills are **cumulative** meaning that skills acquired at a given level are required at the next level. Each skill has been defined operationally by following Bloom's taxonomy of learning objectives (Airasian, P. W. et al. A Taxonomy for Learning, Teaching, and Assessing: A Revision of Bloom's Taxonomy of Educational Objectives. (Longman, New York, NY, USA, 2001)).

This framework can be freely **reused** and serves as inspiration for defining the competencies or prerequisites of a training course, or for evaluating the level of a student. This content is made available under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (**CC BY 4.0**). Version 1, July 2024.

Terminal, Shell & Unix Command UM1	Structure and Function of a Command within the Directory Tree UM2	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Explain the differences between a terminal and a shell <input type="checkbox"/> Give examples of Unix shells <input type="checkbox"/> Describe the three main syntactic components of a Unix command <input type="checkbox"/> Explain the importance of the space in a Unix command <input type="checkbox"/> Name the command that allows you to display the date <input type="checkbox"/> Indicate the keyboard key used to execute a command in the terminal <input type="checkbox"/> Name the command that displays the content of a directory 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Explain the structure of a filename <input type="checkbox"/> Explain the difference between a directory (or folder) and a file (<i>ls -p</i> command) <input type="checkbox"/> Name the character that serves as a "wildcard" to replace multiple characters, for example, the name of a file <input type="checkbox"/> Explain the difference between <i>ls</i> and <i>ls + arguments</i> <input type="checkbox"/> Explain the role of options in a Unix command <input type="checkbox"/> Give an example of an option for a Unix command <input type="checkbox"/> Describe the two forms of options for a Unix command <input type="checkbox"/> Name the combination of options for the <i>ls</i> command that summarizes file sizes in a human-readable way <input type="checkbox"/> Recall the command that displays the documentation of another Unix command <input type="checkbox"/> Name the option of the <i>ls</i> command that displays the list of files in a detailed format <input type="checkbox"/> Indicate the option of the <i>ls</i> command used to display its help message <input type="checkbox"/> Name the characteristic of an absolute path in Unix <input type="checkbox"/> Differentiate between an absolute path and a relative path <input type="checkbox"/> Identify the root in an absolute path 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Identify the directory separator in a path (absolute or relative) <input type="checkbox"/> Name the command that displays the path of the current directory <input type="checkbox"/> Name the command used to navigate the directory tree <input type="checkbox"/> Explain where the parent directory is located in a Unix path <input type="checkbox"/> Name the command that allows you to navigate within a directory of the directory tree <input type="checkbox"/> Describe the effect of the TAB key when writing a command or a path in a terminal <input type="checkbox"/> Differentiate the usage of the <i>cd</i> command alone versus the <i>cd</i> command followed by an argument <input type="checkbox"/> Explain what the "home" directory is <input type="checkbox"/> Recognize the symbol for the "home" directory <input type="checkbox"/> Use two ways to navigate to a given directory in the directory tree <input type="checkbox"/> Examine your position in the directory tree after a directory change <input type="checkbox"/> Name the command to display the complete content of a text file in the terminal <input type="checkbox"/> Name the command that allows you to list all the Unix commands used in the shell so far <input type="checkbox"/> Which keyboard keys are used to navigate through the shell command history?

Advanced Exploration, Modification of the Directory Tree and Workspace

UM3

- Explain the purpose of the `-L 2` option in the command `tree -d -L 2 /shared`
- Explain the meaning of `..` in a path
- Name the command that allows you to create a directory
- Name the command that allows you to copy a file or a directory
- Explain the syntax of the `cp` command
- Explain the usefulness of `.` in the `cp` command
- Describe the effect of the `-r` option on the `cp` command
- Name the command that allows you to move a file or a directory
- Explain the syntax of the `mv` command
- Explain the difference in the result obtained with the `cp` and `mv` commands
- Name the command that allows you to delete a file
- Recognize the target file of the `rm` command
- Identify the target directory in the `rm -r` command
- Indicate the difference(s) between the `less` and `cat` commands
- Give three examples of keyboard shortcuts related to the `less` command
- Name the command that allows you to display the first lines of a file
- Indicate the option of the `head` command that allows you to display the first X lines of a file
- Indicate the command that displays the last lines of a file
- Indicate the option of the `tail` command that allows you to display the last X lines of a file
- Explain the result returned by the command `"wc filename"`
- Specify the option of the `wc` command that allows you to display the number of lines in a file
- What words is the `wc` command an abbreviation of?

Patterns, Redirection, Pipe, Streams

UM4

- Name the Unix command used to display lines in a file that match a given pattern
- Explain the difference(s) between the `less` and `cat` commands
- Provide an example of using the `grep` command
- Name the option of `grep` that allows you to display the lines that do not contain the searched pattern
- Name the command that allows you to extract a column from a tab-separated text file
- Specify the behavior of `cut` in this command `"cut -f 1-3 genes.bed"`
- Explain the usefulness of the `-d` option in the `cut` command
- List the 2 output streams of a command
- Explain what the `>` sign is used for in a command
- Explain the difference between `>` and `>>`
- Name the incoming stream of a Unix command
- Name the primary use of the `stderr` output
- Give an example of redirecting the error output to a file
- Identify in this command the file that will contain the standard output and the file that will contain the standard error: `"grep tp53 /shared/data/bank/homo_sapiens 1> tp53_genes.txt 2> error.log"`
- Identify in this command the file that will contain the standard output and the standard error: `"grep tp53 genome.txt > tp53_genes.txt 2>&1"`
- Use the `cut` command to extract the first column of a file to a new file
- Name the command that allows you to sort the lines of a file
- Describe the effect of the `-u` option in the `sort` command
- Name the option that allows sorting based on numerical values

Usage of a bioinformatics program UM5	Variables, script, automation UM6	Usage of a computing cluster UM7
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> List the differences between a Bash command and a bioinformatics tool <input type="checkbox"/> Identify the path and version of a bioinformatics tool <input type="checkbox"/> Display the usage, options, and command(s) of a bioinformatics tool <input type="checkbox"/> Distinguish between required and optional arguments of a bioinformatics tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Use a bioinformatics tool with appropriate arguments and parameters <input type="checkbox"/> Combine options of a bioinformatics tool to obtain a specific output <input type="checkbox"/> Fix a command line syntax based on the error message 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Forthcoming

Three other levels will be proposed in a future version of this framework:

UM6 Variables, script, automation

UM7 Usage of a computing cluster

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